

INSIGHTS FROM SOUND: MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING MODELS FOR CHRONIC HEART FAILURE DETECTION VIA HEART SOUND ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT:

We present a method for CHF detection based on heart sounds. The method combines classic Machine-Learning (ML) and end-to-end Deep Learning (DL). The classic ML learns from expert features, and the DL learns from a spectro-temporal representation of the signal. The method was evaluated on recordings from 947 subjects from six publicly available datasets and one CHF dataset that was collected for this study. Using the same evaluation method as a recent PhysoNet challenge, the proposed method achieved a score of 89.3, which is 9.1 higher than the challenge's baseline method. The method's aggregated accuracy is 92.9% (error of 7.1%); while the experimental results are not directly comparable, this error rate is relatively close to the percentage of recordings labeled as "unknown" by experts (9.7%). Finally, we identified 15 expert features that are useful for building ML models to differentiate between CHF phases (i.e., in the decompensated phase during hospitalization and in the recompensated phase) with an accuracy of 93.2%. The proposed method shows promising results both for the distinction of recordings between healthy subjects and patients and for the detection of

different CHF phases. This may lead to the easier identification of new CHF patients and the development of home-based CHF monitors for avoiding hospitalizations

1. INTRODUCTION:

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is a chronic, progressive condition underscored by the heart's inability to supply enough perfusion to target tissues and organs at the physiological filling pressures to meet their metabolic demands. CHF has reached epidemic proportions in the population, as its incidence is increasing by 2% annually. In the developed world, CHF affects 1-2% of the total population and 10% of people older than 65 years. Currently, the diagnosis and treatment of CHF uses approximately 2% of the annual healthcare budget. In absolute terms, the USA spent approximately 35 billion USD to treat CHF in 2018 alone, and the costs are expected to double in the next 10 years. Despite the progress in medical- and device-based treatment approaches in the last decades, the overall prognosis of CHF is still dismal, as 5-year survival rate of this population is only approximately 50%. In the typical clinical course of CHF, we observe alternating episodes of compensated phases,

when the patient feels well and does not display symptoms and signs of fluid overload, and decompensated phases, when symptoms and signs of systemic fluid overload (such as breathlessness, orthopnea, peripheral edema, liver congestion, pulmonary edema) can easily be observed. During the latter episodes, patients often require hospital admission to receive treatment with intravenous medications (diuretics, inotropes) to achieve a successful negative fluid balance and return to the compensation state. Early detection of HF worsening would allow a treating physician to adjust the patient's medical management on an outpatient basis in a timely manner and thus avoid the need for a hospital admission. Currently, an experienced physician can detect the worsening of HF by examining the patient and by characteristic changes in the patient's heart failure biomarkers, which are determined from the patient's blood. Unfortunately, clinical worsening of a CHF patient likely means that we are already dealing with a fully developed CHF episode that will most likely require a hospital admission. Additionally, in some patients, characteristic changes in heart sounds can accompany heart failure worsening and can be heard using phonocardiography. An example of a phonocardiogram (PCG) recording of a healthy subject is presented. In healthy subjects, 2 heart sounds are typically heard (called S1 and S2). S1 is caused by the closure of the mitral valve and ventricular wall in the early systole, S2 is caused by the closure of the aortic and pulmonary valves at the beginning of the diastole. Here, the interval between S1 and S2 is called systole,

i.e., the contraction phase of the cardiac cycle, and the interval between S2 and S1 is called diastole, i.e., the relaxation phase of the cardiac cycle. Additional heart sounds (such as S3 and S4) can be heard in certain cardiac conditions and are never regarded as normal. In the case of CHF (in the course of decompensation), we can often hear a third sound (S3) that typically appears 0.1-0.2 s after the second sound, i.e., S2. Recently, it has been demonstrated that some physiological parameters, such as the occurrence of additional heart sounds or increased blood pressure in the pulmonary circulation, already start to appear several weeks before the CHF patient develops a clinically evident decompensation episode. This is also an important therapeutic window where outpatient-based treatment interventions can reverse CHF deterioration and return the patient to the compensated state without the need for a hospital admission. In recent years, many studies have proposed Machine Learning (ML) approaches for the automatic detection of different heart conditions using PCG signals recorded with a digital stethoscope. Nevertheless, methods that explicitly focus on CHF detection are quite scarce. The typical ML pipeline for the detection of different heart conditions is as follows: segmentation of the signals by detecting the "typical" heart sounds (i.e., S1 and S2), denoising of the signals, extracting individual frequency-domain and time-domain features, and learning a feature-based ML model (e.g., using ML algorithms, such as Random Forest or Support Vector Machine - SVM) that is capable of classifying healthy vs. unhealthy sounds.

Most of the features currently used are based on medical and audio/signal analysis knowledge. However, a PCG recording that sounds unhealthy to one expert may sound healthy to another one; therefore, doctors never diagnose a CHF patient using only heart sounds, but rather use a holistic view of the patient instead (i.e., extensive medical history, blood pressure, laboratory tests, etc.). This uncertainty is one reason why 9.7% of the recordings in the recent PhysioNet cardiology challenge were actually labeled as “unknown” by experts, while the rest of the recordings were labeled as healthy or unhealthy. The recent advancements in Deep Learning (DL) suggest that end-to-end learning (i.e., ML models that learn directly from the raw data and no features are needed) can outperform the classic, feature-based ML. For example, DL has achieved breakthrough performance in tasks such as pattern recognition problems, image processing, natural language processing, speech and audio processing, and sensor data processing. For CHF detection, a successful combination of classic ML and end-to-end DL can outperform each single approach. The classic ML approach learns from a large body of expert-defined features, and the DL approach learns both from a time-domain (the raw PCG signal) representation of the signal and a temporal domain representation (the spectrogram) of the signal. This approach was successful in our previous study of human activity recognition from smartphone sensor data. In addition to distinguishing the CHF patients and healthy individuals, we focus on detecting the CHF state (compensated vs. decompensated)

based on the analysis of heart sound recordings. Our work builds upon the initial studies, where we demonstrated that it is possible to distinguish between healthy individuals and patients in a decompensated CHF episode using a stack of machine learning classifiers and expert features, showing promising results on a limited dataset. We expand upon this approach using a considerably larger patient dataset, including six additional PhysioNet datasets, and an improved ML method that uses end-to-end DL. Furthermore, we investigate the differences in the heart sounds during the transition between the decompensated and recompensated states of CHF, with the aim of developing personalized monitoring models. Early detection of the worsening of CHF has the potential to reduce hospitalizations due to the worsening of the condition, which both improves the quality of life of patients and decreases the financial and logistic burden on the patient and the health system

2. LITERATURE SURVEY:

“Chronic heart failure detection from heart sounds using a stack of machine-learning classifiers,”

Chronic heart failure represents a global pandemic, currently affecting over 26 million of patients worldwide. It is a major contributor in the death rate of patients with cardiovascular diseases and results in more than 1 million hospitalizations annually in Europe and North America. Methods for chronic heart failure detection can be utilized to act preventive, improve early diagnosis and avoid hospitalizations or even life-threatening situations, thus highly

enhance the quality of patient's life. In this paper, we present a machine-learning method for chronic heart failure detection from heart sounds. The method consists of: filtering, segmentation, feature extraction and machine learning. The method was tested with a leave-one-subject-out evaluation technique on data from 122 subjects, gathered in the study. The method achieved 96% accuracy, outperforming a majority classifier for 15 percentage points. More specifically, it detects (recalls) 87% of the chronic heart failure subjects with a precision of 87%. The study confirmed that advanced machine learning applied on real-life sounds recorded with an unobtrusive digital stethoscope can be used for chronic heart failure detection.

“Classification of normal/abnormal heart sound recordings: the PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge 2016,”

In the past few decades heart sound signals (i.e., phono-cardiograms or PCGs) have been widely studied. Automated heart sound segmentation and classification techniques have the potential to screen for pathologies in a variety of clinical applications. However, comparative analyses of algorithms in the literature have been hindered by the lack of a large and open database of heart sound recordings. The PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology (CinC) Challenge 2016 addresses this issue by assembling the largest public heart sound database, aggregated from eight sources obtained by seven independent research groups around the world. The database includes 4,430 recordings taken from 1,072

subjects, totalling 233,512 heart sounds collected from both healthy subjects and patients with a variety of conditions such as heart valve disease and coronary artery disease. These recordings were collected using heterogeneous equipment in both clinical and nonclinical (such as in-home visits). The length of recording varied from several seconds to several minutes. Additional data provided include subject demographics (age and gender), recording information (number per patient, body location, and length of recording), synchronously recorded signals (such as ECG), sampling frequency and sensor type used. Participants were asked to classify recordings as normal, abnormal, or not possible to evaluate (noisy/uncertain). The overall score for an entry was based on a weighted sensitivity and specificity score with respect to manual expert annotations. A brief description of a baseline classification method is provided, including a description of open source code, which has been provided in association with the Challenge. The open source code provided a score of 0.71 (Se=0.65 Sp=0.76). During the official phase of the competition, a total of 48 teams submitted 348 open source entries, with a highest score of 0.86 (Se=0.94 Sp=0.78).

"Speed up deep neural network based pedestrian detection by sharing features across multi-scale models,"

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have now demonstrated state-of-the-art detection performance on pedestrian datasets. However, because of their high computational complexity, detection efficiency is still a frustrating problem even

with the help of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs). To improve detection efficiency, this paper proposes to share features across a group of DNNs that correspond to pedestrian models of different sizes. By sharing features, the computational burden for extracting features from an image pyramid can be significantly reduced. Simultaneously, we can detect pedestrians of several different scales on one single layer of an image pyramid. Furthermore, the improvement of detection efficiency is achieved with negligible loss of detection accuracy. Experimental results demonstrate the robustness and efficiency of the proposed algorithm.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

Chronic heart failure (CHF) affects over 26 million of people worldwide, and its incidence is increasing by 2% annually. Despite the significant burden that CHF poses and despite the ubiquity of sensors in our lives, methods for automatically detecting CHF are surprisingly scarce, even in the research community

Disadvantages of Existing System:

- Less Accuracy
- A soft first heart sound is present in congestive heart failure or with prolonged atrioventricular (AV) conduction

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is a chronic, progressive condition underscored by the heart's inability to supply enough perfusion to target tissues and organs at the

physiological filling pressures to meet their metabolic demands [1]. CHF has reached epidemic proportions in the population, as its incidence is increasing by 2% annually. In the developed world, CHF affects 1-2% of the total population and 10% of people older than 65 years. Currently, the diagnosis and treatment of CHF uses approximately 2% of the annual healthcare budget.

Advantages of Proposed System:

- High Accuracy.
- For emergency department patients with shortness of breath and a risk of heart failure, physicians usually grab one thing first: a stethoscope.
- It allows them to hear the S3, an abnormal third sound in the heart's rhythm strongly associated with cardiac disease and heart failure.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This work is unique in that it extracts information from the complete heart sound signal, not just a small portion of it. The long-term scale is characterized as the second time scale, and the short-term scale as the first. Heart sounds are broken down into tiny, fixed-sized pieces on the short-term scale, and short-term characteristics are then taken out of those pieces. Long-term features are retrieved from each heart sound instance, and heart sound instances are seen as a whole in the long-term scale. Classification is done for every fragment.

For a comprehensive system architecture aimed at detecting chronic heart failure from heart sounds, a robust framework blending machine learning and end-to-end deep learning is essential. This architecture should encompass several key components to ensure accuracy, scalability, and efficiency.

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules Information:

To implement this project we have designed following modules.

- 1) Upload Physionet Dataset: using this module we will upload dataset to application
- 2) Dataset Preprocessing: using this module we will extract audio recording features and systolic and diastolic features from dataset and then normalize values
- 3) Run ML Segmented Model with FE & FS: using this module we will extract and select systolic and diastolic features from dataset and then train with Random Forest Classic ML model and then apply

test data to calculate its prediction accuracy

- 4) Run DL Model on Raw Features: using this module we will extract RAW features from recording and then train with deep learning model and then this model will be applied on test data to calculate its accuracy
- 5) Run Recording ML Model: using this module we will extract features from Classic ML model and deep learning model and then retrain with 3rd classifier to get its prediction accuracy
- 6) Predict CHF from Test Sound: using this module we will upload Test Heart Sound file and then classifier model will predict whether given recording file is Normal or Abnormal

7. SCREENSHOTS:

To run project double click on 'run.bat' file to get below screen

Screenshot1: In above screen click on 'Upload Physionet Dataset' button to upload dataset

Screenshot2: In above screen selecting and uploading ‘Dataset’ folder and then click on ‘Select Folder’ button to load dataset and to get below output

normal or abnormal. Now close above graph and then click on ‘Run ML Segmented Model with FE & FS’ button to train Classic ML segmented model on above dataset and get below output

Screenshot5: In above screen with Classic ML we got 90% accuracy and now click on ‘Run DL Model on Raw Features’ to get below output

Screenshot3: In above screen dataset loaded and now click on ‘Dataset Preprocessing’ button to read all dataset file and then extract features from it

Screenshot6: In above screen with DL model we got 93% accuracy and in graph x-axis represents epoch or iterations and y-axis represents accuracy or loss values and green line represents accuracy and blue line represents LOSS and we can see with each increasing epoch accuracy got increase and loss got decrease and now close above graph and then click on ‘Run Recording Model’ button to get below output

Screenshot4: In above screen we can see dataset contains 405 heart sound files from 405 different person and 117 are the Normal sound and 288 are abnormal and in graph x-axis represents normal or abnormal and y-axis represents number of persons for

Screenshot7: In above screen with recording model we got 96% accuracy and we can see all algorithms performance graph in below screen

Screenshot8: In above graph x-axis represents algorithm names and y-axis represents accuracy, sensitivity and specificity and in all algorithms Recording model has got high accuracy. Now close above graph and then click on 'Predict CHF from Test Sound' button to upload test sound file and get predicted output as Normal or Abnormal

Screenshot9: In above screen selecting and uploading '1.wav' file and then click on 'Open' button to get below output

Screenshot10: In above screen uploaded heart sound file predicted as ABNORMAL and similarly you can upload other files and test

Screenshot11: For 2.wav' file below is the output

8. CONCLUSION:

In this paper, we presented a novel method for CHF detection from PCG audio

recordings. The method combines classic ML and end-to-end DL. The classical ML learns from a large body of expert-defined features and the DL learns both from the time-domain (i.e., the raw PCG signal) representation of the signal and the spectral representation of the signal. We evaluated the method on our own dataset for CHF detection and additionally on six publicly available PhysioNet datasets used for the recent PhysioNet Cardiology Challenge. The challenge datasets allowed us to extensively evaluate the performance of the method on similar domains. The evaluation results on all the datasets showed that, compared to the challenge baseline methods, our method achieves the best performance (see the PhysioNet experiments section). The facts that most of these datasets are labeled for different types of heart-related conditions and that the PCG audio is recorded from a different body position in most of the datasets (e.g., aortic area, pulmonic area, tricuspid area, and mitral area) strongly indicate that the proposed method is quite robust and that it is useful for detecting different types of heart-sound classification problems and not just for CHF detection, as long as domain-specific labeled data are provided. Finally, we extended the study beyond the typical healthy vs. patient classification and explored personalized models for detecting different CHF phases, i.e., the recompensated phase (i.e., when the patient feels well) and the decompensated phase (i.e., when the patient needs medical attention). We identified 15 features that have different distributions depending on the phase. By using just two of these features, we were able to build a simple and

transparent decision tree classifier (see Fig. 3) that is capable of distinguishing between the recompensated and the decompensated phases with an accuracy of 93.2%, calculated using a LOSO evaluation. While we are aware that there is a risk of overfitting in these final experiments, especially since the dataset contains only 44 samples, we believe that these results are very encouraging and represent a solid base for further development of personalized models. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to address such a problem.

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